

A few results for solving a certain class of ordinary differential equations

Gautam Barua
Department of Civil Engineering
Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati
Guwahati - 781039, India
Email: g_barua@iitg.ac.in

This note (non-peer reviewed) presents a few mathematical results which may be used for solving a certain categories of ordinary differential equations.

Theorem-1A

Suppose an n^{th} – order ordinary differential equation:

$\psi(x, y(x), y'(x), y''(x), y'''(x), \dots, y^{(n)}(x)) = 0$ with n (where n , naturally, is finite and ≥ 1) boundary conditions has a unique and exact solution $y(x)$ in the interval $[0,1]$, where ψ is any linear or non-linear functions of $x, y(x), y'(x), y''(x), y'''(x), \dots, y^{(n)}(x)$. Suppose $y(x)$ and $\psi(x)$ and their derivatives to any order are continuous and bounded in $[0,1]$ [i.e., $y(x), y'(x), \dots, y^{(k)}(x)$ and $\psi(x), \psi'(x), \dots, \psi^{(k)}(x)$ are all continuous and bounded in $[0, 1]$, where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ (set of natural numbers) and $\rightarrow \infty$ and $y^{(k)}(x)$ and $\psi^{(k)}(x)$ are the k -th derivative of $y(x)$ and $\psi(x)$, respectively at x ; also, there exists an M ($0 < M < \infty$) such that $|y^{(k)}(x)| < M$ and $|\psi^{(k)}(x)| < M \forall x \in [0,1]$ and for all k ($k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$; $y^{(0)}$ and $\psi^{(0)}$ here mean $y(x)$ and $\psi(x)$, respectively)]. Suppose also that $y^{(k)}(x)$ are not all zero $\forall x \in [0,1]$ after some k (where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\rightarrow \infty$). Then the solution of the differential equation can be obtained in terms of a polynomial function by making use of the boundary condition(s) and the $\psi(x)$ function along with its derivatives, the degree of the polynomial being dependent on the extent of accuracy desired in the solution.

Proof:

We first show that, under the assumptions of the theorem, the exact solution $y(x)$ has a polynomial representation of any extent of accuracy that we desire. Indeed, if $P_e(x)$ be the $(N + n) - 1$ degree Taylor representation of $y(x)$ being developed with respect to any arbitrary point x_p of $[0,1]$, the error term of the expansion can then be expressed as

$$|y(x) - P_e(x)| = \left| \frac{y^{(N+n)}(\xi_2)(x - x_p)^{(N+n)}}{(N+n)!} \right| \leq \left| \frac{y^{(N+n)}(\xi_2)}{(N+n)!} \right| < \frac{M}{(N+n)!}, \text{ where } 0 \leq \xi_2 \leq 1. \text{ Naturally,}$$

by choosing a sufficiently large value of N , say N_ε (where $N_\varepsilon \in \mathbb{N}$), $|y(x) - P_e(x)|$ can always be made less than any chosen $\varepsilon > 0$. Further, as this N_ε depends only on ε and not on any $x \in [0,1]$, $P_e(x)$ also converges uniformly to $y(x)$ in $[0,1]$. Thus, under the assumptions of the theorem, a uniformly convergent polynomial representation of any desired accuracy can always be worked out of $y(x)$, even when the exact solution is not originally of polynomial form.

We now show that this polynomial expansion of $y(x)$ can also be obtained by carrying out a ‘zero-expansion’ of $\psi(x)$ with respect to a point or multiple set of points belonging to the interval $[0,1]$. Let $P_a(x) = C_0 + C_1x + C_2x^2 + \dots + C_{(N+n)-1}x^{(N+n)-1}$ be a $(N+n)-1$ degree polynomial with $(N+n)$ unknown C_i s, where $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, [(N+n)-1]$. Using the n boundary conditions on it, n equations can first be obtained. Now under the assumptions of the theorem,

the multiple integrals of $\int_0^x dx_N \int_0^{x_N} dx_{N-1} \dots \int_0^{x_2} dx_1 \psi^{(N)}(x_1)$ is possible in $[0,1]$; this yields an

$$\text{expression } \int_0^x dx_N \int_0^{x_N} dx_{N-1} \dots \int_0^{x_2} dx_1 \psi^{(N)}(x_1)$$

$$= \psi(x) - \left[\psi(0) + x\psi'(0) + \frac{x^2}{2!}\psi''(0) + \dots + \frac{x^{N-1}}{(N-1)!}\psi^{(N-1)}(0) \right].$$

If $\psi(0), \psi'(0), \dots, \psi^{(N-1)}(0)$ are equated individually to zero, that would provide us the remaining equations for evaluating the C_i

$$s \text{ and then we get, by applying the mean-value theorem } |\psi(x)| = \left| \int_0^x dx_N \int_0^{x_N} dx_{N-1} \dots \int_0^{x_2} dx_1 \psi^{(N)}(x_1) \right|$$

$$= \left| \frac{x^N}{N!} \psi^{(N)}(\zeta_3) \right| < \frac{M}{N!}, \text{ where } 0 \leq \zeta_3 \leq 1. \text{ Thus, for any given } \varepsilon > 0, \text{ an } N_\varepsilon \in \mathbb{N} \text{ can be}$$

determined such that $|\psi(x)|$ will be less than this $\varepsilon \forall N \geq N_\varepsilon$ and $\forall x \in [0,1]$. As N_ε depends only on ε and not on the x_i s $\in [0,1]$, C_i s thus can be determined such that $\psi(x)$ converges uniformly to zero to any desired level of accuracy in $[0,1]$. This shows that $P_a(x)$ can be made to satisfy the considered differential equation to any desired accuracy. Further, because of the uniqueness of the solution, both $P_e(x)$ [the polynomial representation of $y(x)$] and $P_a(x)$ [the polynomial obtained via ‘zero-expansion’ of $\psi(x)$] would be the same polynomial where it should be noted that in each of these polynomials, $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Let us now extend our multi-integral analysis to two points, say 0 and 1 $\in [0,1]$. $P_a(x)$ can now be considered as a polynomial of degree $[(2N+n)-1]$ with $(2N+n)$ unknowns C_i s (i.e., i now runs from $i=0$ to $i=[(2N+n)-1]$). Like before, the n boundary conditions give n equations. Now, by equating the $2N$ terms $\psi(0), \psi'(0), \dots, \psi^{(N-1)}(0)$ and $\psi(1), \psi'(1), \dots, \psi^{(N-1)}(1)$ individually to zero, the remaining $2N$ equations can next be obtained. The necessary equations to evaluate the C_i s, thus, can be obtained this way. Once the C_i s are being evaluated

$$\text{this way, we will then have the relation } \int_0^x dx_N \int_0^{x_N} dx_{N-1} \dots \int_0^{x_2} dx_1 \psi^{(N)}(x_1)$$

$$- \int_1^x dx_N \int_1^{x_N} dx_{N-1} \dots \int_1^{x_2} dx_1 \psi^{(N)}(x_1) = 0. \text{ The modulus of the remainder terms, in view of the}$$

$$\text{remainder theorem, will then be } \left| \frac{x^N}{N!} \psi^{(N)}(\zeta_4) \right| = \left| \frac{(x-1)^N}{N!} \psi^{(N)}(\zeta_5) \right|, \text{ where } 0 \leq \zeta_4 \leq 1 \text{ and}$$

$0 \leq \zeta_5 \leq 1$. From this, it is obvious that the maximum error on $\psi(x)$ on its two-point ‘zero-expansion’ on $[0,1]$ will then be $|\psi(x)| = \left| \frac{x^N}{N!} \psi^{(N)}(\zeta_4) \right| = \left| \frac{(x-1)^N}{N!} \psi^{(N)}(\zeta_5) \right| < \frac{M}{N!} \left(\frac{1}{2^N} \right)$, which,

as may be observed, is a reduction of a factor of $\left(\frac{1}{2^N} \right)$ when compared to the one-point

expansion of $\psi(x)$ at the point $x=0$. The procedure can be extended by adding any number of distinct points $\in [0,1]$ in the $\psi(x)$ example. For example, if $\psi(x)$ expansion is being carried at three distinct points $0, 1$ and $x_3 \in [0,1]$, the maximum absolute error on $\psi(x)$ will then be less

than the maximum of $\left\{ \frac{M}{N!} \left(\frac{x_3}{2} \right)^N, \frac{M}{N!} \left(\frac{|x_3-1|}{2} \right)^N \right\}$, where x_3 and $|x_3-1|$ are all less than one.

As the maximum of $\left\{ \frac{M}{N!} \left(\frac{x_3}{2} \right)^N, \frac{M}{N!} \left(\frac{|x_3-1|}{2} \right)^N \right\} < \frac{M}{N!} \left(\frac{1}{2^N} \right)$, it is obvious that three-point

expansion is inducing lesser error than the two-point expansion and, of course, than the one-point expansion as well. It should be noted that for the three-point expansion, $P_a(x)$ will be a

polynomial of $[(3N+n)-1]$ degree with $(3N+n)$ unknown C_i s and that to generate the necessary number of equations to evaluate the C_i s, apart from the boundary conditions, $\psi(j)$, $\psi'(j), \dots, \psi^{(N-1)}(j)$ terms would need to be individually equated to zero, where $j=0,1$ and x_3 .

If the procedure is generalized to N_g distinct points $0, 1, x_3, \dots, x_{N_g} \in [0,1]$ (we name this set as S_D and call the distinct points in it as ‘developing points’) then $[0,1]$ will be partitioned into $N_g - 1$ intervals and the maximum absolute error on $\psi(x)$ will then be less than

$\frac{M}{N!} \times \text{Maximum of} \left(\frac{|x_r - x_s|}{2} \right)^N \forall x \in [0,1]$, where $|x_r - x_s|$ is the largest gap length between any

two arbitrary adjacent points x_r and $x_s \in S_D$ in the $N_g - 1$ partitioned $[0, 1]$ space. Thus, for a

fixed N , the error on $|\psi(x)|$ for $\forall x \in [0,1]$ is dependent on how closely the points on S_D are being distributed *throughout the whole space* $[0, 1]$ and not on only a portion or portions of the $[0, 1]$ space. Also, when S_D has N_g distinct points (i.e., when $[0, 1]$ is being divided into

$N_g - 1$ intervals), $P_a(x)$, naturally, will then be a polynomial of $[(N_g N) + n] - 1$ degree.

Further, from the inequality $|\psi(x)| < \frac{M}{N!} \times \text{Maximum of} \left(\frac{|x_r - x_s|}{2} \right)^N$, it is clear that $\psi(x)$

converges to zero uniformly $\forall x \in [0,1]$ if $N \rightarrow \infty$ or the largest gap length $|x_r - x_s|$ between any two adjacent points in $S_D \rightarrow 0$ or both. This means, even for $N=1$, $\psi(x)$ will converge to zero in $[0, 1]$ provided $|x_r - x_s| \rightarrow 0$. This is an important observation as this greatly relaxes the assumptions of the theorem in the sense that $\psi(x)$ need not have to be $\mathbb{C}^k$ (where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and

$\rightarrow \infty$), C^1 continuity is enough for this function. In view of the same, a generalized form of Theorem-1A can be expressed as follows (considering the importance of this form of the theorem, it is being put under a ‘REMARK’ heading).

REMARK-I

Theorem-1B [Generalized form when $y(x)$ does not have a finite polynomial representation]

Suppose an n^{th} – order ordinary differential equation:

$\psi(x, y(x), y'(x), y''(x), y'''(x), \dots, y^{(n)}(x)) = 0$ with n boundary conditions has a unique and exact solution $y(x)$ in the interval $[0,1]$, where ψ is any linear or non-linear functions of $x, y(x), y'(x), y''(x), y'''(x), \dots, y^{(n)}(x)$. Suppose $y(x)$ and their derivatives to any order are continuous and bounded in $[0,1]$ and that $\psi(x)$ and $\psi'(x)$ are also continuous and bounded in $[0,1]$ [i.e., $y(x), y'(x), \dots, y^{(k)}(x)$ and $\psi(x)$ and $\psi'(x)$ are all continuous and bounded in $[0, 1]$, where $k \in \mathbb{N}$ (set of natural numbers) and $\rightarrow \infty$ and $y^{(k)}(x)$ is the k -th derivative of $y(x)$ and at x ; also, there exists an M ($0 < M < \infty$) such that $|y^{(k_1)}(x)| < M$ and $|\psi^{(k_2)}(x)| < M \forall x \in [0,1]$ for $k_1 = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ and $k_2 = 0$ and 1 (where $y^{(0)}$ and $\psi^{(0)}$ mean $y(x)$ and $\psi(x)$, respectively)] then the solution of the differential can be obtained in terms of a polynomial function by making use of the boundary condition(s) and the $\psi(x)$ function alone, the degree of the polynomial being dependent on the extent of accuracy desired in the solution.

We will now show that the set of ‘developing points’ S_D in $[0,1]$ can be taken in $[0,1]$ in such a way that it is dense in $[0,1]$.

Proof:

Suppose $N_g \rightarrow \infty$ and let the elements of S_D are all rational numbers in $[0,1]$, i.e.,

$S_D = \{0, 1, x_3, x_4, \dots\}$, where $0, 1, x_i$ ($i \rightarrow \infty$) are all rational numbers in $[0,1]$. Now from standard real analysis results, $\bar{S}_D = [0, 1]$. Indeed, if x_p be any point $\in [0, 1]$, an open interval centered on x_p with any radius $\varepsilon > 0$ ($0 < |x - x_p| < \varepsilon$) will, as per the ‘density theorem’ always have an element of S_D inside it (however small ε may be); this is true whether $x_p \in S_D$ or $x_p \in [0,1] \setminus S_D$. Thus, $\bar{S}_D = S_D \cup S'_D = [0, 1]$, where S'_D is the set of limit points of S_D . Thus, S_D is dense in $[0,1]$. Also, as S_D is countable, $[0,1]$, as is well known, is a separable space.

We will now be dealing with situations where the exact solution $y(x)$ has a finite polynomial representation, say of degree $N_f - 1$, where $N_f \geq 1$, finite and $\in \mathbb{N}$. For this situation, naturally, $y^{(k)}(x) = 0 \forall k \geq N_f$ (where x is any arbitrary number $\in [0,1]$). We will, then have for this case, a Taylor expansion [say $P_{x_p}(x)$], with respect to any point, say $x_p \in [0,1]$, such that

$$|y(x) - P_{x_p}(x)| = \left| \frac{y^{N_f}(\xi_1)(x - x_p)^{N_f}}{N_f!} \right| = 0 \quad \forall x \in [0,1], \text{ where } 0 \leq \xi_1 \leq 1. \text{ It should be noted that the}$$

same polynomial would have been generated had the Taylor expansion been carried out with

respect to a different point, say $x_q \in [0,1]$. This is because as $y(x)$ is unique, $P_{x_p}(x) = P_{x_q}(x) \forall x \in [0,1]$, where $P_{x_q}(x)$ is the Taylor expansion obtained with respect to the point $x_q \in [0,1]$; further, by the properties of polynomials, the corresponding coefficients of the polynomials $P_{x_p}(x)$ and $P_{x_q}(x)$ would also be same. Thus, for this situation, $|y(x) - P_{x_p}(x)| < \varepsilon$ for any arbitrary $\varepsilon > 0$ and $y(x) = P_{x_p}(x) = P_{x_q}(x) \forall x \in [0,1]$. Let us now try to simulate the exact finite polynomial solution $y(x)$ by our procedure as mentioned above; towards this end, let us define a finite polynomial $P_f(x)$ as $P_f(x) = C_0 + C_1x + C_2x^2 + \dots + C_{N_f-1}x^{N_f-1}$, where C_i s ($i = 0$ to $N_f - 1$) are constants needed to be determined. Now, there can be two possibilities, namely, $N_f \leq n$ or $N_f > n$. If $N_f \leq n$, the n boundary condition(s) is (are) sufficient to evaluate the constant(s) of the $P_f(x)$ polynomial and there is no need to utilize the $\psi(x)$ function and/or its derivatives to generate any more equations for evaluating the constants of the polynomial. Also, as $\psi(x)$ and its derivatives will be all zero $\forall x \in [0,1]$ for this case, $P_f(x) = y(x)$, as $y(x)$ is unique. On the other hand, if $N_f > n$, then we need to generate $N_f - n$ additional equation(s) (i.e., apart from those obtained from the n boundary conditions) to evaluate the constants of $P_f(x)$. This can be easily done, again by using the $\psi(x)$ function and its derivative(s). Since $\psi^{(\alpha)}(x) = 0 \forall \alpha \geq N_f - n$ and $\forall x \in [0,1]$ (where $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}$) for this situation, $\psi(x)$ will thus converge to zero $\forall x \in [0,1]$. Also, as $y(x)$ is unique by assumption, $P_f(x) = y(x) \forall x \in [0,1]$. We can also see that for this situation (i.e., when N_f is finite and $> n$) also, the $\psi(x)$ function alone can be used to generate the additional $N_f - n$ equation(s) [i.e., its derivative(s) is(are) not required]. To show this, let us choose our $P_f(x)$ to be initially of a much higher degree than $N_f - 1$, say of $N_t - 1$ degree (where $N_t \in \mathbb{N}$, is finite and $> N_f$), and then get the required $N_t - n$ equations from the $\psi(x)$ function by considering a large (but finite) number of uniformly distributed distinct points of $[0,1]$ in S_D and forcing $\psi(x)$ to be zero at these points. This will give us our solution and since $y(x)$ is unique, all C_i s from $i = N_f$ to N_t would be zero. Thus, the final solution $P_f(x)$ will be a $N_f - 1$ polynomial only. The same result would be obtained if a different set of points is taken in S_D and $\psi(x)$ is forced zero at these points. But then this tells that $P_f(x)$ can be obtained by using the n boundary conditions and making $\psi(x)$ zero at any $N_f - n$ *arbitrarily distributed distinct points only* (the gap between these points need not tend to zero) in $[0,1]$. Also, as $y(x)$ is unique, $P_f(x)$ will be equal to it. In view of the above discussions, Theorem-1A and Theorem-1B, when $y(x)$ has a finite polynomial representation, can be expressed as follows (again, because of the importance of this version of the theorem, it is being placed under a ‘REMARK’ heading)

REMARK-II

Theorem-1C [Generalized form when $y(x)$ has a finite polynomial representation]

Suppose an n^{th} – order ordinary differential equation:

$\psi(x, y(x), y'(x), y''(x), y'''(x), \dots, y^{(n)}(x)) = 0$ with n boundary conditions has a unique and exact solution $y(x)$ in the interval $[0,1]$, where ψ is any linear or non-linear functions of

$x, y(x), y'(x), y''(x), y'''(x), \dots, y^{(n)}(x)$. Suppose $y(x)$ and their derivatives to any order are continuous in $[0,1]$ and suppose $\forall x \in [0,1], y^{(k)}(x) = 0 \quad \forall k \geq N_f$, where N_f is finite, ≥ 1 and $\in \mathbb{N}$ (set of natural numbers), $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $y^{(k)}(x)$ means the k -th derivative of $y(x)$ at x .

Further, suppose $\psi(x)$ and $\psi'(x)$ are also continuous in $[0,1]$. Then the solution of the differential equation can be obtained exactly in the form of a $N_f - 1$ degree polynomial by making use of (i) only the boundary condition(s) if $1 \leq N_f \leq n$, (ii) the boundary condition(s) and the $\psi(x)$ function along with its derivative(s) or the boundary condition(s) and the $\psi(x)$ function alone, if $N_f > n$.

Also, if $y(x) = P_f(x)$ has a finite polynomial representation, then from well known results, we see that term by term differentiation and integration of $y(x) = P_f(x)$ is possible. Further, if

$y(x) = P_a(x)$ does not have a finite polynomial representation, then also, in view of the assumptions of the theorem, term by term differentiation and integration of $y(x) = P_a(x)$ is possible. Indeed, if $y_N(x)$ is the sum of first N terms of $y(x)$ [say

$y_N(x) = u_1(x) + u_2(x) + \dots + u_N(x)$] and $r_N(x)$ is its remainder term [say

$r_N(x) = u_{N+1}(x) + u_{N+2}(x) + \dots$], then $\int_0^c y(x)dx - \int_0^c y_N(x)dx = \int_0^c r_N(x)dx$, where $0 < c \leq 1$. Since

N is finite and u_i s ($i = 1$ to N) are all polynomial functions differentiable in $[0, 1]$, term by term integration of $y_N(x)$ is possible. Also, as $y(x)$ (due to the assumptions of the theorem) converges uniformly in $[0, 1]$, we have for a chosen $\varepsilon > 0$, an $N_\beta \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\forall x \in [0, 1]$

$|r_N(x)| < \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \quad \forall N \geq N_\beta$. Thus, we have

$$\left| \int_0^c y(x)dx - \int_0^c y_N(x)dx \right| = \left| \int_0^c y(x)dx - \left[\int_0^c u_1(x)dx + \int_0^c u_2(x)dx + \dots + \int_0^c u_N(x)dx \right] \right| = \left| \int_0^c r_N(x)dx \right|$$
$$\leq \int_0^c |r_N(x)|dx < \varepsilon. \quad \text{This shows that } \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left[\int_0^c u_1(x)dx + \int_0^c u_2(x)dx + \dots + \int_0^c u_N(x)dx \right] = \int_0^c y(x)dx \text{ and}$$

we thus have $\int_0^c y(x)dx = \int_0^c u_1(x)dx + \int_0^c u_2(x)dx + \dots + \int_0^c u_N(x)dx + \dots$

Further, since $u_1(x), u_2(x), \dots$ all have continuous derivatives in $[0, 1]$, then again from well known results, we see that the term by term differentiation of $y(x)$ is also possible.

REMARK-III

If a differential equation defined in an interval $[a, b]$ obeys the statements of Theorem-1A or Theorem-1B or Theorem-1C, then everything what have been said above are also applicable to this differential equation as well. It should be noted that a differential equation defined in $[a, b]$ can be easily reduced to the interval $[0, 1]$ by applying the mapping function

$X(x) = \left(\frac{1}{b-a}\right)(x-a)$, where x and X are the variables associated with the $[a, b]$ and $[0, 1]$ spaces, respectively.

Lemma 1

Let $A = (a_{ij})$ be an n -dimensional square matrix, where i and j belong to the set $S_n = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and where $a_{ij} \neq 0 \forall i$ and $j \in S_n$. Let the elements of a_{ij} be such that $a_{1j} = (C)^{e(j)}$ and $a_{gj} = (m_{g-1}C)^{e(j)}$, where $C \neq 0$, $j \in S_n$, $g \in G_n = \{2, 3, \dots, n\}$ and where $e(j)$ s are all finite numbers such that $e(j_1) \neq e(j_2) \forall j_1 \neq j_2$ (j_1 and $j_2 \in S_n$) and where m_{g-1} s are all finite numbers such that $m_{g-1} \neq 0, \neq 1 \forall g \in G_n$ and $m_{g_1-1} \neq m_{g_2-1} \forall g_1 \neq g_2$ (g_1 and $g_2 \in G_n$). Under these definitions of a_{ij} , we claim (for finite n , of course) that $\det(A) \neq 0$ (and A is thus invertible).

Proof:

We have, by definition, $\det(A) = |A| = \sum_{\sigma \in S_n} (\text{sign } \sigma) a_{1\sigma(1)} a_{2\sigma(2)} \dots a_{n\sigma(n)}$, where σ belongs to all

possible permutations of the elements of S_n . If A is being reduced by standard determinant operations into its upper or lower triangular form, then $|A|$ will be of the form

$(\text{sgn } \sigma) a_{1\sigma(1)} b_{2\sigma(2)} \dots b_{n\sigma(n)}$, where $b_{i\sigma(i)}$ ($i_1 = 2, 3, \dots, n$) are the reduced diagonal elements of a_{ij} being obtained after transforming the matrix to its upper or lower triangular form. Since for this situation $\sigma(i_1) = i_1$, the sign of σ would hence be positive (since σ is the identity permutation).

We thus have the expression for the determinant as $|A| = a_{11} b_{22} \dots b_{nn}$. If $m_{g_1-1} = 0$ for a $g_1 \in G_n$, some row of the a_{ij} matrix will then be zero as per the conditions of the lemma. This, in turn,

would mean that $|A|$ would then be zero. Thus, $m_{g-1} \neq 0 \forall g \in G_n$. For a 2×2 matrix with our

definition of a_{ij} , the determinant will be $|A| = (C)^{[e(1)+e(2)]} \times (m_1)^{[e(1)]} [(m_1)^{[e(2)-e(1)]} - 1]$, which,

naturally, would not be zero as per the stated conditions of the lemma. For determinants of size greater than 2, the upper triangulation (the proof may also be approached by considering lower triangulation) of a_{ij} (i.e., by reducing the elements below the diagonal to zero) by standard

determinant operations gives us the expression

$$|A| = \left\{ \frac{[a_{21} a_{31} a_{32}^{(1)} a_{41} a_{42}^{(1)} a_{43}^{(2)} \dots (a_{n1} a_{n2}^{(1)} a_{n3}^{(2)} \dots a_{nn}^{(n-1)})]}{(a_{11})^{n-2} (a_{22}^{(1)})^{(n-1)-2} \dots (a_{(n-2)(n-2)}^{(n-3)})^{(n-3)}} \right\}, \text{ where } a_{pq}^{(k)} = \left[\frac{a_{pq}^{(k-1)}}{a_{pk}^{(k-1)}} \right] a_{kk}^{(k-1)} - a_{kq}^{(k-1)}, k = 1, 2, \dots$$

$(n-1)$, $p, q > k$, $n \geq 3$ and where $a_{pq}^{(0)}$ is considered as a_{pq} . Now consider the term $a_{pq}^{(1)}$, where p and q are both > 1 and both take on all the values from 2 to n . From the previous expression,

we get $a_{pq}^{(1)} = a_{1q} \left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}}{a_{p1}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{11}}{a_{1q}} \right) - 1 \right] = (C)^{e(q)} \left[(m_{p-1})^{e(q)-e(1)} - 1 \right]$. It should be noted that the C

terms are getting cancelled inside the square bracket leaving only the m terms behind inside the bracket. Further for each p (where $p > 1$ and goes up to n), $(m_{p-1})^{e(q)-e(1)} \neq 1$ as q runs from 2 to n . This is because $m_{g-1} \neq 1 \forall g \in G_n$ and $e(j_1)$ s are all finite and $e(j_1) \neq e(j_2)$

$\forall j_1 \neq j_2$ (j_1 and $j_2 \in S_n$). Also, $(C)^{e(q)} \neq 0$ as C , by assumption, is finite and non-zero. Thus, $a_{pq}^{(1)} \neq 0 \forall p$ and q , where p and q , as mentioned before, are both > 1 . Again from the $a_{pq}^{(k)}$

expression, we have for $k = 2$, $a_{pq}^{(2)} = a_{2q}^{(1)} \left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(1)}}{a_{p2}^{(1)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{22}^{(1)}}{a_{2q}^{(1)}} \right) - 1 \right] = a_{1q} \left[\left(\frac{a_{2q}}{a_{21}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{11}}{a_{1q}} \right) - 1 \right]$

$\times \left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(1)}}{a_{p2}^{(1)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{22}^{(1)}}{a_{2q}^{(1)}} \right) - 1 \right]$, which in expanded would be $a_{pq}^{(2)} = (C)^{e(q)} \left[(m_1)^{e(q)-e(1)} - 1 \right]$

$\times \left\{ \frac{(m_{p-1})^{e(q)-e(1)} - 1}{(m_1)^{e(q)-e(1)} - 1} \left[\frac{(m_1)^{e(2)-e(1)} - 1}{(m_{p-1})^{e(2)-e(1)} - 1} \right] - 1 \right\}$. As $(C)^{e(q)} \neq 0$ for any q , it can be seen from the

last expression that $a_{pq}^{(2)}$ s will also be not equal to zero for any p and q so long p and q are both > 2 . In this context, it should be noted that even though $a_{pq}^{(1)}$ s are not equal to zero when p

and q are both > 1 , the term $\left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(1)}}{a_{p2}^{(1)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{22}^{(1)}}{a_{2q}^{(1)}} \right) - 1 \right]$ will be zero when p and/or q take(s) on the

value 2; this is because, in that case the ratio term $\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(1)}}{a_{p2}^{(1)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{22}^{(1)}}{a_{2q}^{(1)}} \right)$ will be one. Thus, $a_{pq}^{(2)}$ will be

not zero only when p and q are both > 2 . Again from the $a_{pq}^{(k)}$ relation, we find

$a_{pq}^{(3)} = (C)^{e(q)} \left[\left(\frac{a_{2q}}{a_{21}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{11}}{a_{1q}} \right) - 1 \right] \left[\left(\frac{a_{3q}^{(1)}}{a_{32}^{(1)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{22}^{(1)}}{a_{2q}^{(1)}} \right) - 1 \right] \left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(2)}}{a_{p3}^{(2)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{33}^{(2)}}{a_{3q}^{(2)}} \right) - 1 \right]$. Here also, we see that even

though $a_{pq}^{(2)}$ s are not zero when p and q are both > 2 , the term $\left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(2)}}{a_{p3}^{(2)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{33}^{(2)}}{a_{3q}^{(2)}} \right) - 1 \right]$ will be so

when p and/or q are/is equal to 3. Thus, for this situation also, $a_{pq}^{(3)} \neq 0$ only when both p and

q are > 3 . Let us now assume that $a_{pq}^{(k)} \neq 0$ for $k = n-2$ when p and q are $> n-2$. We have

already seen that for $k=1$ and p and $q > 1$, for $k=2$ and p and $q > 2$ and for $k=3$ and p

and $q > 3$, $a_{pq}^{(k)} \neq 0$. Now from our $a_{pq}^{(k)}$ relation, we find for $k = n-1$,

$a_{pq}^{(n-1)} = (C)^{e(q)} \left[\left(\frac{a_{2q}}{a_{21}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{11}}{a_{1q}} \right) - 1 \right] \left[\left(\frac{a_{3q}^{(1)}}{a_{32}^{(1)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{22}^{(1)}}{a_{2q}^{(1)}} \right) - 1 \right] \left[\left(\frac{a_{4q}^{(2)}}{a_{43}^{(2)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{33}^{(2)}}{a_{3q}^{(2)}} \right) - 1 \right] \dots \left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(n-2)}}{a_{p(n-1)}^{(n-2)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{(n-1)(n-1)}^{(n-2)}}{a_{(n-1)q}^{(n-2)}} \right) - 1 \right]$.

Here also, as may be observed, the $\left[\left(\frac{a_{pq}^{(n-2)}}{a_{p(n-1)}^{(n-2)}} \right) \left(\frac{a_{(n-1)(n-1)}^{(n-2)}}{a_{(n-1)q}^{(n-2)}} \right) - 1 \right]$ term is becoming zero if p and/or q are/is equal to $n-1$, even though $a_{pq}^{(n-2)}$ s are not zero for p and $q > n-2$ (by our assumption). Thus, $a_{pq}^{(n-1)} \neq 0$ only when both p and $q > n-1$. This shows that if $a_{pq}^{(k)} \neq 0$ for $k = n-2$ when p and q are $> n-2$, then $a_{pq}^{(k)} \neq 0$ for $k = n-1$ as well when p and q are both $> n-1$. Thus, by the law of Induction, $a_{pq}^{(k)} \neq 0 \forall k$ as long as p and q are $> k$, where $k = 1, 2, \dots, (n-1)$. Thus, $|A| \neq 0$ (and hence A is invertible) when the square matrix a_{ij} of the size $n \times n$ is being generated as per the stated conditions of the lemma.

The lemma as stated above may be of help if an attempt is being made to obtain a series solution of an ordinary differential equation based on the mathematical results as mentioned above.

Applications

We will now show a few applications of our theorems in the form of two examples.

Example-1 Consider first a very simple differential equation $\frac{dy}{dx} = x^2$, $y(0) = 0$. The exact

solution (y_{ex} say) of it, naturally, is $y_{ex} = \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)x^3$. To show how a solution of the differential

equation can be attempted based on Theorem-1A, let us first assume the solution of it as $y = K_0 + K_1(x) + K_2(x)^2 + K_3(x)^3 + K_4(x)^4$, where K_i ($i = 0$ to 4) are constants needed to be determined. $\psi(x)$ for this assumed solution would be

$\psi(x) = \frac{dy}{dx} - x^2 = [K_1 + 2K_2(x) + 3K_3(x)^2 + 4K_4(x)^3] - x^2$. As can be seen, the boundary

condition $y(0) = 0$ gives $K_0 = 0$. Also, as per our procedure, four equations required to evaluate the constants may be obtained by forcing $\psi(x)$, $\psi'(x)$, $\psi''(x)$ and $\psi'''(x)$ to be zero at $x = 0$. If we do that and solve the ensuing equations, we will get the K_i s as $K_1 = 0$, $K_2 = 0$, $K_3 = \frac{1}{3}$ and

$K_4 = 0$ and the y then, naturally, will be $\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)x^3$. But this is exactly the same expression as the

exact solution y_{ex} . It is to be noted that if the solution has been assumed to be a polynomial of higher degree than four [in that case $\psi(x)$ would need to be differentiated more than three times to generate the necessary number of equations for evaluating the K_i s], then also, as can be checked, the same result would have been obtained, i.e., then also, all the K_i s would have been

zero except K_3 which would be $\frac{1}{3}$. Theorem-1C also says that a solution can also be attempted

of the differential equation by making use of the $\psi(x)$ function alone, i.e., without utilizing its higher derivatives. Thus forcing $\psi(x)$ alone to be zero at any four arbitrary points in $(-\infty, +\infty)$

[see the explanations leading to 'REMARK-II'; also note that our differential equation here satisfies all the requirements of Theorem-1C in $(-\infty, +\infty)$] and solving the resultant equations

should give us the K_i ($i = 0$ to 4) of our solution. As may be checked, that is exactly what is happening. For example, if we force $\psi(x)$ to be zero at, say $x = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 and solve the resultant equations, we find the K_i s as $K_1 = 0, K_2 = 0, K_3 = \frac{1}{3}$ and $K_4 = 0$; if we take the x_i s ($i = 0$ to 4) as $x = -1, -2, -3$ and -4 and solve the equations obtained from them, as may be checked, we still find the K_i s as $K_1 = 0, K_2 = 0, K_3 = \frac{1}{3}$ and $K_4 = 0$ and so on. Like before, we can also start with a solution polynomial with degrees more than four; in that case, we need to take more number of developing points to generate the necessary number of equations to evaluate the K_i s but the final result, as can be checked, will still be the same, i.e., y will still be equal to the exact solution $\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)x^3$ only.

Suppose we are now interested to have a solution of $\frac{dy}{dx} = x^2, y(0) = 0$ in an extended way in the domain $0 \leq x \leq 1$ [as already mentioned ('REMARK-III'), a differential equation can always be reduced to a normalized domain though simple substitution of variables]. To start with, let us take a second degree polynomial $y_1 = B_0 + B_1(x) + B_2(x)^2$ as a solution of our differential equation, where B_0, B_1 and B_2 are constants needed to be determined. For this considered polynomial, $\psi_1(x)$ (say) $= \frac{dy}{dx} - x^2 = B_1 + 2B_2(x) - x^2$. Also, from the boundary condition, we find $B_0 = 0$; thus, we need to determine B_1 and B_2 only using the $\psi_1(x)$ function. Now, as per Theorem-1B, we can consider any two (two here because there are only two unknowns) arbitrary well spread points in $0 \leq x \leq 1$ to generate two equations out of the $\psi_1(x)$ function. For simplicity, let us take these points as $x = 0$ and $x = 1$. Evaluation of $\psi_1(x)$ at the former point would then give us B_1 as 0 and at the later point B_2 as $\frac{1}{2}$. Thus, we have then our approximate

solution y_1 as $y_1 = \frac{1}{2}(x)^2$. From Table 1 it is clear that this is not a good solution at all of our differential equation. Let us now extend our solution and take it as $y_2 = y_1 + C_1(1.5 - x)^{0.5} + C_2(1.5 - x)^{1.5} + C_3(1.5 - x)^{2.5} + C_4(1.5 - x)^{3.5}$, where C_1, C_2, C_3 and C_4 are constants to be determined. It should be noted that each of the power functions $(1.5 - x)^{(\cdot)}$ with non-integral exponents can be developed into a polynomial form to any desired degree in $0 \leq x \leq 1$ by Taylor expansions; thus, the C_i s ($i = 1$ to 4) can be viewed as getting multiplied to polynomials only. Of course, any other power functions capable of being expanded in polynomial forms in $0 \leq x \leq 1$ could have been taken; however, the non-integral power function extensions that we have considered here are often computationally quite handy in evaluating the C_i s than extension of the solution carried out with integral power functions.

Now, the $\psi(x)$ term for y_2 can be written as $\psi_2(x)$ (say) $= \frac{dy_2}{dx} - x^2 = \frac{dy_1}{dx} +$

$\frac{d}{dx} \left[C_1(1.5-x)^{0.5} + C_2(1.5-x)^{1.5} + C_3(1.5-x)^{2.5} + C_4(1.5-x)^{3.5} - x^2 \right]$, where, as may be observed, y_1 is already known. The four equations required for evaluating the C_i s can next be obtained by forcing y_2 to be zero at $x = 0$ (boundary condition) and by forcing $\psi_2(x)$ to be zero at any three arbitrarily well spread points in $[0, 1]$. Let us take these three points as 0, 0.5 and 1 (of course, any other three well distributed points can also be taken). Solving these four equations, we find the C_i s as $C_1 = -0.26470588235294$, $C_2 = -0.17647058823529$, $C_3 = 0.58823529411765$ and $C_4 = -0.23529411764706$. With the C_i s known, y_2 is thus determined. From Table 1, we see that y_2 indeed is a much accurate solution than y_1 and is, in fact, matching up to the second places of decimal with the exact solution at most of the tested points. Let us now further extend our solution by adding a few more power functions to y_2 and consider it as

$y_3 = y_2 + D_1(1.5-x)^{0.25} + D_2(1.5-x)^{1.25} + D_3(1.5-x)^{2.25} + D_4(1.5-x)^{3.25} + D_5(1.5-x)^{4.25} + D_6(1.5-x)^{5.25}$, where y_3 is the name given to the new solution. The $\psi(x)$ function will now be $\psi_3(x)$ (say) $= \frac{dy_3}{dx} - x^2 = \frac{dy_2}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx} \left[D_1(1.5-x)^{0.25} + D_2(1.5-x)^{1.25} + D_3(1.5-x)^{2.25} + D_4(1.5-x)^{3.25} + D_5(1.5-x)^{4.25} + D_6(1.5-x)^{5.25} \right]$. The six equations for evaluating the

D_i s ($i = 1$ to 6) (it should be noted that y_2 is already known) can next be obtained from the boundary condition $y_3(0) = 0$ and by forcing $\psi_3(x)$ to be zero at five arbitrary well spread points in $[0, 1]$; let us choose these points as 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1 (of course some other five point set in $[0, 1]$ can also be taken). The six equations thus obtained can then be solved; solving the same, we get the D_i s as $D_1 = 0.06011771909623$, $D_2 = -0.3375598047149$, $D_3 = 0.67142824643780$, $D_4 = -0.5766994729421$, $D_5 = 0.21439026807477$ and $D_6 = -0.02679594724406$; y_3 thus is being determined. From Table 1, it can be seen that at the tested points, y_3 predictions are virtually same as those obtained from the exact solution. We have considered a very simple differential equation to illustrate the $\psi(x)$ approach; however, the same methodology can be adopted to solve a highly complex differential equation as well so long the requirements of theorems as mentioned above are being fulfilled by the same. It is to be noted that as the $\psi(x)$ approach does not involve differentiating a differential equation multiple number of times in its application, it may prove to be computationally less demanding in solving a differential equation in many instances than where higher derivatives of $\psi(x)$ are also being utilized to solve it. This is specifically true for differential equations which are highly non-linear in nature.

Table 1. Comparison of predictions as obtained from the derived solutions with those obtained from the exact solution at a few points in $[0, 1]$ for the differential equation as considered in Example-1.

	x				
	0	0.25	0.5	0.75	1
y_1	0	0.0313	0.1250	0.2813	0.5000
y_2	0	0.0025	0.0368	0.1380	0.3336
y_3	0	0.0052	0.0416	0.1406	0.3333
y_{ex}	0	0.0052	0.0417	0.1406	0.3333

Example-2 Let us now consider the zero order Bessel differential equation

$x^2 \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + x \frac{dy}{dx} + x^2 y = 0$ in the domain $[0,1]$ with the boundaries at the ends as $y(0) = J_0(0) = 1$

and $y(1) = J_0(1)$, respectively, where $J_0(0)$ and $J_0(1)$ are the values of the zero order Bessel function of first kind at $x = 0$ and $x = 1$, respectively. An attempt will now be made to obtain a 'first kind' solution of it in the domain $[0,1]$ utilizing the results of Theorem-1A. As in the first example, we start by first assuming a polynomial solution of the problem by including the boundary conditions in the defined polynomial itself; thus, it can be written as

$$y^{(5)} = J_0(0) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + J_0(1) \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + C_1^{(5)} [x(x-1)] + C_2^{(5)} [x(x-1)^2] + C_3^{(5)} [x(x-1)^3] \\ + C_4^{(5)} [x(x-1)^4] + C_5^{(5)} [x(x-1)^5], \text{ where } C_i \text{ s are the constants to be determined and the}$$

superscript 5 in y and the constants, simply means that we are dealing with a five degree polynomial solution here. It should be noted that this way assuming a solution to the problem is not mandatory and is done as an illustration only; a solution to the problem can very well be obtained by choosing the polynomial in it and forcing the boundary conditions on the same, in a

different way as well. $\psi(x)$ for this problem can be expressed as $\psi(x) = x^2 \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + x \frac{dy}{dx} + x^2 y$

and the five equations needed to evaluate the constants can be obtained from the relations

$\psi^{(1)}(x=0) = 0$, $\psi^{(2)}(x=0) = 0$, $\psi^{(3)}(x=0) = 0$, $\psi^{(4)}(x=0) = 0$ and $\psi^{(5)}(x=0) = 0$, where $\psi^{(i)}$ means the i^{th} derivative of ψ . It may be observed that, for this differential equation, the

$\psi(x)$ function is anyway zero at $x = 0$; thus, forcing $\psi(x)$ to be zero at $x = 0$ is not yielding any equation for this differential equation. Also, for this case, the derivatives of $\psi(x)$ at $x = 0$

can be expressed as $\psi^{(1)}(x=0) = \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_{x=0}$ and

$\psi^{(n)}(x=0) = (n^2) \left(\frac{d^n y}{dx^n}\right)_{x=0} + [n(n-1)] \left(\frac{d^{n-2} y}{dx^{n-2}}\right)_{x=0}$ for $n \geq 2$. Now, plugging $y^{(5)}$ in

$\psi^{(i)}(x=0) = 0$ ($1 \leq i \leq 5$) and solving the resulting equations, we find the constants of our five

degree polynomial solution as $C_1^{(5)} = 1.12924530 \ 604889$, $C_2^{(5)} = -0.3556864 \ 3702668$,

$C_3^{(5)} = -0.2519264\ 2775728$, $C_4^{(5)} = 0.05403965\ 331118$ and $C_5^{(5)} = 0.02300405\ 331010$. In the same way, an eight degree polynomial solution of the differential equation can also be obtained. Thus, if $y^{(8)} = J_0(0) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + J_0(1) \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + C_1^{(8)}[x(x-1)] + C_2^{(8)}[x(x-1)^2] + C_3^{(8)}[x(x-1)^3] + C_4^{(8)}[x(x-1)^4] + C_5^{(8)}[x(x-1)^5] + C_6^{(8)}[x(x-1)^6] + C_7^{(8)}[x(x-1)^7] + C_8^{(8)}[x(x-1)^8]$ is an assumed solution of the differential equation, the constants of the polynomial, like before, can also be obtained by forcing $\psi^{(i)}$ ($1 \leq i \leq 8$) to be zero at $x = 0$ with the assumed solution (i.e., with $y^{(8)}$) and then solving the ensuing equations obtained from these operations. Performing these calculations, we find the constants of this solution as $C_1^{(8)} = 1.13071665\ 074651$, $C_2^{(8)} = -0.34952835\ 768351$, $C_3^{(8)} = -0.24330159\ 002384$, $C_4^{(8)} = 0.05628971\ 624769$, $C_5^{(8)} = 0.01742045\ 016827$, $C_6^{(8)} = -0.00547576\ 120757$, $C_7^{(8)} = -0.00167558\ 673517$ and $C_8^{(8)} = -0.00009538\ 851805$. From Table 2 it can be seen that predictions from both $y^{(5)}$ and $y^{(8)}$ are matching very closely with those obtained from the exact solution and that $y^{(8)}$ predictions, expectedly, are an improvement over those of $y^{(5)}$ predictions differing from the exact values in the upward of sixth and seventh places of decimals only for all the compared points.

As a further example involving the Bessel differential equation, let us now consider the modified form of it and try to obtain a few solutions of the same in the domain $[0, 1]$ using our results.

Thus, we have now the differential equation $x^2 \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + x \frac{dy}{dx} - x^2 y = 0$ with the defined

boundaries at the ends as $y(0) = I_0(0) = 1$ and $y(1) = I_0(1)$, where $I_0(0)$ and $I_0(1)$ are the values of the zero order modified Bessel function of first kind at $x = 0$ and $x = 1$, respectively.

As can be observed, this differential equation is very similar to our previous differential equation except that, unlike the earlier equation, we have now a negative sign in front of the third term.

Also, we have now $\psi_m(x) = x^2 \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + x \frac{dy}{dx} - x^2 y$ (the subscript m simply means that this

function is related to the modified differential equation here) and here also $\psi_m(x)$, as may be observed, is zero at $x = 0$. Further, for this case also, the derivatives of $\psi_m(x)$ at $x = 0$ can also

be expressed in a generalized way; they are as $\psi_m^{(1)}(x = 0) = \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_{x=0}$ and

$\psi_m^{(n)}(x = 0) = (n^2) \left(\frac{d^n y}{dx^n}\right)_{x=0} - [n(n-1)] \left(\frac{d^{n-2} y}{dx^{n-2}}\right)_{x=0}$ for $n \geq 2$. Now, like in the previous case, a

five degree polynomial solution (named as $y_m^{(5)}$, say) for this problem can also be worked by first assuming a solution of the same degree, forcing $\psi_m^{(i)}$ to be zero at $x = 0$ ($1 \leq i \leq 5$) with this assumed solution and then solving the resultants equations obtained from them. By carrying out

these operations, we find $y_m^{(5)}$ as $y_m^{(5)} = I_0(0) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + I_0(1) \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + C_{1m}^{(5)}[x(x-1)]$

$$+ C_{2m}^{(5)} [x(x-1)^2] + C_{3m}^{(5)} [x(x-1)^3] + C_{4m}^{(5)} [x(x-1)^4] + C_{5m}^{(5)} [x(x-1)^5],$$

where $C_{1m}^{(5)} = 2.13234177\ 500560$, $C_{2m}^{(5)} = -0.24029110\ 327716$, $C_{3m}^{(5)} = -0.3802429\ 5998316$, $C_{4m}^{(5)} = 0.02979688\ 875766$ and $C_{5m}^{(5)} = 0.02613860\ 071128$. In the same way [i.e., by forcing $\psi_m^{(i)}$ to be zero at $x = 0$ ($1 \leq i \leq 8$)], an eight degree polynomial solution (named as $y_m^{(8)}$, say) of the modified Bessel function can also be easily determined; it works out as

$$y_m^{(8)} = I_0(0) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + I_0(1) \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + C_{1m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)]$$

$$+ C_{2m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)^2] + C_{3m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)^3] + C_{4m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)^4] + C_{5m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)^5] + C_{6m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)^6]$$

$$+ C_{7m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)^7] + C_{8m}^{(8)} [x(x-1)^8], \text{ where } C_{1m}^{(8)} = 2.13592271\ 178940,$$

$$C_{2m}^{(8)} = -0.2238204\ 1314248, \quad C_{3m}^{(8)} = -0.35177739\ 946419, \quad C_{4m}^{(8)} = 0.05039712\ 676454,$$

$$C_{5m}^{(8)} = 0.02796496\ 281039, \quad C_{6m}^{(8)} = -0.00532741\ 611503, \quad C_{7m}^{(8)} = -0.00230318\ 577313 \text{ and}$$

$$C_{8m}^{(8)} = -0.00017383\ 839779. \text{ It should be noted that the subscript } m \text{ used in } y_m^{(5)}, y_m^{(8)} \text{ and the}$$

constants of these solutions, like in the $\psi_m(x)$ function, simply means that they are related to the solution of the modified Bessel differential equation only and not to the ordinary Bessel differential equation as considered earlier. Table 3 shows that predictions from both $y_m^{(5)}$ and $y_m^{(8)}$ are in very close agreement with those obtained from the exact solution; also, as thought of, predictions from $y_m^{(8)}$ are relatively more accurate than those of $y_m^{(5)}$ even though $y_m^{(5)}$

predictions, as can be seen, are quite accurate in themselves. We have restricted here in the solutions of both the ordinary and modified Bessel differential equations up to a polynomial of eight degree only; this is because, as can be observed in Tables 2 and 3, both $y^{(8)}$ and $y_m^{(8)}$ are pretty accurate solutions of these differential equations and the extent of accuracy achieved in them probably is sufficient for most practical uses of these equations. However, the procedures as mentioned above can very well be applied to obtain polynomial solutions of any degree that we desire for both the differential equations (i.e., ordinary as well as modified Bessel differential equations of zero degree) that we have considered in this example. Further, these equations can also be solved using the $\psi(x)$ function alone (Theorem-1B) as has been shown in Example-1.

Also, if

$$y^{(n)} = J_0(0) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + J_0(1) \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + C_1^{(n)} [x(x-1)] + C_2^{(n)} [x(x-1)^2] + \dots + C_n^{(n)} [x(x-1)^n] \text{ and}$$

$$y_m^{(n)} = I_0(0) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + I_0(1) \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + C_{1m}^{(n)} [x(x-1)] + C_{2m}^{(n)} [x(x-1)^2] + \dots + C_{nm}^{(n)} [x(x-1)^n] \text{ are}$$

n^{th} degree polynomial solutions of the ordinary as well as modified Bessel differential equations, then an expression for evaluation of π can be expressed as

$$\frac{\pi}{2} = \left(\frac{1}{J_0(1) - I_0(1)} \right) \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \left[C_{1m}^{(n)} J_0(1) - C_1^{(n)} I_0(1) \right] - \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} \left[\frac{J_0(1)I_0(x) - J_0(x)I_0(1)}{x-1} \right] \right\}. \text{ If we take } n$$

as 8 and use the $C_1^{(8)}$ and $C_{1m}^{(8)}$ values from the $y^{(8)}$ and $y_m^{(8)}$ expressions in this equation, a very approximate value of π can then be worked out.

Table 2. Comparison of predictions as obtained from the derived solutions with those obtained from the exact solution at a few points in $[0, 1]$ for the ordinary Bessel differential equation of first kind zero order as considered in Example-2.

	x				
	0.10	0.30	0.50	0.70	0.90
$y^{(5)}$	0.99750156429164	0.97762740206746	0.93848582572722	0.88126555537780	0.80760943314357
$y^{(8)}$	0.99750156206607	0.97762624692420	0.93846983494878	0.88120123597627	0.80752492046076
$J_0(x)$	0.99750156206604	0.97762624653830	0.93846980724081	0.88120088860741	0.80752379812254

Table 3. Comparison of predictions as obtained from the derived solutions with those obtained from the exact solution at a few points in $[0, 1]$ for the modified Bessel differential equation of first kind zero order as considered in Example-2.

	x				
	0.10	0.30	0.50	0.70	0.90
$y_m^{(5)}$	1.00250156719177	1.02262917589229	1.06351663924936	1.12644442315435	1.21318425637781
$y_m^{(8)}$	1.00250156293412	1.02262687977109	1.06348340117063	1.12630340355239	1.21298642226922
$I_0(x)$	1.00250156293410	1.02262687935160	1.06348337074132	1.12630301830681	1.21298516572868

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